

Fabrication and Evaluation of Polyurethane Nanocomposites with Plasma-Modified Carbon Nanotubes

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Introduction

Nanocarbon: nano-sized carbon material

High thermal conductivity and mechanical strength

However

- Strong van der Waals forces, easy to aggregate
- Poor interfacial interaction

Introduction

Improved dispersibility

Surfactants

Physical properties are difficult to increase

Chemical modifications

Complicated process
Too much filler loss

Introduction

Surface modification by plasma treatment

Simple process
low loss

Isocyanate groups are imparted by plasma

Plasma treatment Carbon nanotubes(pCNT)

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Introduction

pCNTs

Polyurethanes(PU)

Fabrication of polyurethane composites

Introduction

solution mixing method

Agglomerate

Introduction

This study

In-situ polymerization

Matrix: Polyurethane (PU)

Filler: Carbon nanotubes (CNT)

PU/CNT Composites

Sample Preparation

Synthesis of PU/CNT composites

Polyol: Polytetramethylene oxide
Isocyanate: Hexamethylene diisocyanate

Sample Preparation

Polyurethane molding

Results & discussion

Figure Optical images of PU and various PU/CNTs nanocomposites

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Figure. SEM images of PU and PU/CNT composite materials

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Figure. Thermogravimetric curves of PU and PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Results & discussion

Figure. Pyrolysis temperatures of PU and PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Results & discussion

Figure. Stress-strain curves of PU and various PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Results & discussion

Figure. Elastic modulus of PU and various PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Results & discussion

Figure. Tensile strength of PU and various PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Results & discussion

Figure. Fracture strain of PU and various PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Results & discussion

Figure. Toughness of PU and various PU/CNTs nanocomposites

Conclusions

In very small quantities, the film maintained transparency, but in smaller quantities, agglomerates were seen.

Thermophysical properties showed a high rate of increase for small volume fills.

In terms of mechanical properties, both elastic moduli showed a high rate of increase, while other properties showed a high rate of increase for very small volume fillings.

Thank you for your attention.

